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ENDING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN ACADEMIA

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SUMMARY

This report presents a complete proposal for a monitoring framework including a practical tool and indicators for monitoring national/regional policies to counteract gender-based violence in the European Research Area (ERA).

The monitoring framework and tool were developed in consultation with relevant stakeholders in the ERA, specifically the members of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and the GenderSAFE Community of Practice circle of National Authorities.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

7P	7P model: policy, prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, partnership, provision of services
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GBV	Gender-based violence
HE	Higher Education
HEI(s)	Higher education institution(s)
LGBTQIA+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, queer/questioning, intersex, asexual, and other
NA	National authority
NGO(s)	Non-governmental organisation(s)
R&I	Research and innovation
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 ABOUT THIS MONITORING FRAMEWORK AND TOOL

This monitoring framework has been developed in the context of the EU-funded GenderSAFE project and serves to facilitate the monitoring of policies to counteract gender-based violence at the national/regional level of EU Member States and Associated Countries.

Specifically, GenderSAFE Work Package 5 is dedicated to data collection and monitoring on measures to counteract gender-based violence and Task 5.2 focuses on the development and piloting of a methodology for data collection and monitoring of national/regional policies with a view to obtaining harmonised and comparable information at the EU level. The monitoring aims to allow an easy check on whether a policy is in place and what its elementary features are. It focuses on the policy adoption stage (and not implementation).

The monitoring tool reflects the recent policy advancement, specifically the adoption of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct (European Commission 2024), as the latest policy document on the issue of gender-based violence in the European Research Area (ERA) addressing, among other stakeholders, the Member States. The Zero-tolerance code of conduct reflects the scholarly state of the art, most significantly the conceptualisation of violence as gendered, based on gender power and inequality, occurring along a continuum, and the 7P approach developed in the UniSAFE project (Mergaert et al. 2023). It also addresses the types of actions that are needed to counteract gender-based violence in a comprehensive manner.

The purpose of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct is “to provide guidance to Member States, stakeholders, and individuals on how to create a European Research and Innovation (R&I) environment free from all forms of gender-based violence, based on the values of gender equality and inclusiveness, respect, dignity and safety.” (European Commission 2024, p. 3). Therefore, the monitoring tool reflects the principles defined in Section 5 of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

The monitoring tool also builds on the results of two specific tasks in the GenderSAFE project. First, it builds on Task 2.1, the objective of which was to review the conceptualisation of zero tolerance (Bondestam et al. 2024). Second, it draws on Task 2.3, which operationalises the Zero-tolerance code of conduct. This allows monitoring of the introduction of gender-based violence policies at the national level in the EU, their broad contents and alignment with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct. In addition, considered in the course of development of the monitoring tool was the Horizon Europe approach to the GEP eligibility criterion in the General Annexes and specifically how the four obligatory building blocks are formulated.

This document contains the background information on the development of the methodology, a glossary of terms used in the methodology, the methodology itself and the indicators used for monitoring national/regional policies at the EU level, which national/regional authorities have put in place at the national/regional level to address gender-based violence.

1.2 ABOUT GENDERSAFE

The EU-funded GenderSAFE project promotes zero-tolerance for gender-based violence in the ERA and supports research and higher education institutions in establishing safe, inclusive and respectful environments by setting up comprehensive policies. It builds on the insights and operational tools developed within the UniSAFE project to advance efforts to implement a zero-tolerance approach to gender-based violence in the ERA.

Project objectives:

- Strengthening zero-tolerance policies in the EU by developing a unified policy discourse that reflects cutting-edge theoretical debates, with a focus on power dynamics, intersectionality, mobility, and precarity.
- Encouraging the adoption of zero-tolerance policies on gender-based violence through co-design and mutual learning in a Community of Practice.
- Developing institutional capacities to set up and implement gender-based violence policies by training dedicated staff.
- **Creating a knowledge base on the adoption and details of zero-tolerance policies in the EU using a comprehensive data collection and monitoring system.**

The present report contributes to the realisation of the fourth objective, indicated in bold above.

2. GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN THE ERA: POLICY CONTEXT

Ending gender-based violence is a cornerstone of the European Union's commitment to a **Union of Equality**, a priority set out by European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen. As part of this commitment, the **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025**, adopted on 8 March 2020, establishes the prevention and elimination of gender-based violence as one of its central objectives. The strategy pledges that “the EU will do all it can to prevent and counteract gender-based violence, support and protect victims of such crimes, and hold perpetrators accountable for their abusive behaviour,” and calls on Member States to systematically collect and report data on such violence.

On 14 May 2024, [Directive \(EU\) 2024/1385](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council on counteracting violence against women and domestic violence was adopted.

Significantly, the EU as a whole acceded to the [Council of Europe's Istanbul Convention](#) in June 2023, which is the most comprehensive international treaty on preventing and counteracting violence against women and domestic violence. This accession entered into force on 1 October 2023. At the national level, all EU Member States have signed the Convention, and 21 have ratified it.

2.1 ZERO-TOLERANCE CODE OF CONDUCT

In the context of **research and innovation policy**, addressing gender-based violence is increasingly recognised as critical to achieving inclusive, safe and equitable research environments.

In 2021, 37 parties including 25 Member States endorsed the [Ljubljana Declaration](#) on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation, which defined six priorities one of which is gender-based violence.

Box 2. Ljubljana Declaration on gender-based violence

Gender-based violence

Gender-based violence in higher education and research, including sexual harassment, is a serious and under-recognised issue with severe negative impacts on study and career outcomes in research and higher education. A cohesive infrastructure and procedures for preventing and tackling gender-based violence and harassment in academia in the Member States and other countries are missing.

There is a prominent lack of relevant policies, legislation/regulations, responsible authorities, gender-based violence/sexual harassment experts, gender-sensitive protocols and reporting procedures and up-to-date prevalence data. To this end, we welcome that gender-based violence is included as part of data collection practices for She Figures, and as a thematic area to be addressed in Gender Equality Plans. Furthermore, we recognise there is need for additional policy coordination and action from Research Funding Organisations, Research Performing Organisations and other relevant stakeholders in the European Research Area.

The Ljubljana Declaration served as the backbone for the development of actions in the [ERA Policy Agenda 2022 – 2024](#) in ERA Action 5 “PROMOTE GENDER EQUALITY AND FOSTER INCLUSIVENESS, TAKING NOTE OF THE LJUBLJANA DECLARATION”.

The **ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024** was adopted in November 2021 and altogether sets out 20 concrete actions to deepen the European Research Area (ERA). ERA Action 5 explicitly aims to support the development and implementation of inclusive Gender Equality Plans and to **prevent gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in research and innovation organisations**. The defined outcome for this element was: “[Strategy to counteract gender-based violence including sexual harassment in the European R&I system and to assure gender equal and inclusive working environments through institutional change in any research funding or performing organisation.](#)” Within the framework of this work, the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality drafted and adopted the [Zero-tolerance code of conduct](#) (European Commission 2024) to counteract gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in the EU research and innovation system.

2.2 OTHER SIGNIFICANT DEVELOPMENTS

The **Council Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe**, adopted by the Competitiveness Council on 8 December 2023, explicitly highlights the need to address persisting gender inequalities, including gender-based violence.

The **revised European Charter for Researchers**, annexed to the Recommendation, incorporates specific references under two key principles:

- Under “[Working conditions, funding and salaries](#)”: Employers are expected to ensure working environments that support mental and physical wellbeing, including “appropriate procedures for preventing and tackling gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.”
- Under the principle of “[Gender Equality](#)”: Gender equality is explicitly linked to the fight against gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

The [European Parliament Resolution on Young Researchers](#), adopted on 14 December 2023, underscores the vulnerability of early-career researchers to harassment and abuse. It calls on Member States to ensure transparent and fair procedures in academic systems to address these risks, particularly given the reliance of young researchers on the support of senior colleagues for career advancement.

A further development at EU level is the pending **Council Decision encouraging Member States to ratify the ILO Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019 (No. 190)**. In January 2024, the European Parliament’s FEMM and EMPL Committees gave their consent, with co-rapporteurs emphasising that violence and harassment stem from broader societal inequalities, including power dynamics, gender norms and systemic discrimination.

Within the **European Commission itself**, a revised **Decision on the prevention of and fight against psychological and sexual harassment** was adopted on 12 December 2023. It takes a victim-centred approach, with a strong focus on early intervention, mandatory

managerial training, and bystander education, demonstrating the Commission's intent to lead by example.

Finally, the **Gender Equality Plan (GEP) eligibility criterion** introduced in Horizon Europe serves as a key policy lever. To be eligible for funding, public research organisations, higher education institutions and public bodies in Member States and Associated Countries must have a GEP in place. Among the recommended areas for action in GEPs are “[measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.](#)”

Together, these policy developments signal growing political and institutional recognition of the need to address gender-based violence in research and innovation systems, both to safeguard individuals and to uphold the values of excellence, integrity and equality that underpin the ERA.

3. THE MONITORING METHODOLOGY: PURPOSE, DESIGN, MAIN FEATURES AND DATA COLLECTION

3.1 THE MONITORING METHODOLOGY

The three key monitoring terms used in this monitoring methodology are to be understood as follows:

- **The monitoring framework** is the conceptual structure that presents and clarifies the main components of the monitoring tool and what exactly it monitors and how, what type of information will be collected and how, and the proposed indicators.
- **The monitoring mechanism** consists of a monitoring tool together with the plan for the organisation of data collection via an online data collection instrument, to be completed primarily by the members of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and/or ERA Forum.
- **The monitoring tool** is a questionnaire, which is the actual instrument that is used for data collection, processing, and reporting for the purpose of monitoring.

3.2 THE PURPOSE OF THE MONITORING METHODOLOGY

The Zero-tolerance code of conduct (European Commission 2024) adopted in September 2024 by the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality provides an ambitious and shared understanding of what is required to counteract gender-based violence in the ERA. As such, along with the explicit commitments to gender equality and gender mainstreaming, including counteracting gender-based violence, it represents the foundation for the design and implementation of the monitoring framework and the monitoring tool.

The design of the monitoring framework focuses on monitoring the implementation of commitments made by Member States and Associated Countries in their national/regional systems, not the implementation of the policies. As such, it focuses on the policy adoption stage.

The purpose of the monitoring framework is to propose an EU-wide, state-of-the-art approach to monitoring national/regional policies on counteracting gender-based violence and their features, and thus provide a basis for creating an overview of policies at the policy-adoption stage across the EU.

3.3 THE DESIGN PROCESS OF THE MONITORING METHODOLOGY

The design process of the monitoring framework included the following stages:

- (1) Review of inputs for development of the monitoring tool: UniSAFE analyses (Fajmonová et al. 2021), GENDERACTIONplus studies and position papers (Bondestam et al. 2023, 2024; GENDERACTIONplus 2024a, 2024b), EU baseline Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

- (2) A review of existing national-level monitoring of gender-based violence policies with a focus on France, Ireland and Spain within the scope of Task 5.1 of the GenderSAFE project.
- (3) Designing a monitoring framework with a set of indicators that capture the commitments to counteract gender-based violence in line with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.
- (4) Designing the monitoring tool.
- (5) Piloting the monitoring framework and tool at a feedback event with members of the ERA Forum Subgroup on Inclusive Gender Equality.
- (6) Revision of the tool for a second round of feedback.
- (7) Second round of feedback from members of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and members of the GenderSAFE circle of national authorities.
- (8) Internal quality review within the GenderSAFE project.

The feedback session under (5) was designed to primarily engage the ERA Forum Subgroup on Inclusive Gender Equality, implementing ERA Action 5, which includes representatives from the European Commission, Member States, and relevant ERA umbrella organisations. Members of the National Authorities circle created within the GenderSAFE Community of Practice have also been invited to the feedback session. This feedback session took place online on 26 February 2025 from 10:00 CET to 13:00 CET, with 10 participants.

After the revision of the framework and the tool, a second round of feedback has been solicited from members of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality and the Gender CoP circle of National Authorities. This feedback opportunity was provided between 4 and 16 April 2025 in writing.

3.4 THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE MONITORING METHODOLOGY

The three pillars of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct (Commitment, Action and Accountability) provide the structure of the monitoring framework.

The points of departure for the development of the monitoring framework and tool were:

- The Commitment to the Zero-tolerance code of conduct as the foundation for the implementation of the monitoring framework and tool.
- The comprehensive nature of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct building on the currently most comprehensive theoretical and conceptual tool, the UniSAFE 7P model.
- Comprehensive and flexible approach to monitoring reflecting the variability across national/regional systems.
- Reliance for data collection on the ERA governance structures (the ERA Forum Subgroup on Inclusive Gender Equality and the ERA Forum).
- Stakeholder consultation (the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality, the Circle of National Authorities within the GenderSAFE project).

The monitoring framework is structured around four elements: the existence of laws, policies and initiatives as the first element, followed by the three pillars of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct (Commitment, Action and Accountability).

The monitoring tool is intended to be completed by public authorities based on self-reporting.

The tool contains 43 questions in total, with 15 in Section 1 Existence of laws/policies/initiatives, 3 in Section 2 Commitment, 8 (required institutional actions) + 8 (recommended institutional actions) in Section 3 Action, and 9 in Section 4 Accountability. The approximate time to answer the questionnaire will depend significantly on the existence of laws/policies/initiatives in place at the national level. If the laws/policies/initiatives are less comprehensive, the time required can be 30 minutes (depending on familiarity with concepts). In the event of more comprehensive policies, the time to completion can be up to 2 hours.

A technical solution will be sought that will allow to temporarily save a draft and go back to previous questions.

The structure of the monitoring tool

The monitoring tool is a questionnaire structured in four sections as indicated above. Each section contains a series of questions to establish the existence or not of specific elements in the national/regional policy. Answers to these questions will feed the assessment of the situation at the national/regional level. A traffic light system will be used on a five-point scale: Comprehensive – Developing – Intermediary – Emerging – Absent.

Some questions are accompanied by open-ended options for providing additional information, in order to capture any other information that is relevant to the national/regional situation.

The traffic light categorisation included below in the four sections of the questionnaire is included in this technical policy framework to facilitate an understanding for prospective users who will be completing the questionnaire of how policy adoption and evolution will be presented in the analytical report. This rating will be applied by GenderSAFE based on the responses provided in the questionnaire.

Policy outlook. At the end of the first section, there are additional questions asking for an assessment of the policy outlook. This indicator reflects existing plans to modify legislation and adopt new policies that intend to further support, or undermine, the existing policy. The degree to which these plans have been put in practice can be assessed in the next monitoring cycle, checking back on the outlook in this way. This indicator is meant to monitor not only the situation at a given time in the respective national/regional systems, but also the direction of planned and documented developments regarding policy adoption (positive, negative, unchanged, or mixed). In this way, the monitoring tool can support mutual learning activities and policy dialogue among national and regional authorities in the ERA when new positive initiatives are considered and initiated, and to draw attention to planned developments.

3.5 DATA COLLECTION TOOL AND REPORTING

For the data collection, an online tool will be used to deploy the policy monitoring questionnaire. A report will be prepared analysing the current situation across European countries, including country fiches with country profiles and a thematic comparative overview where possible across the ERA.

4 TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

To facilitate the completion of the monitoring tool, this section provides the definitions of the terms used.

4.1 GENERAL NOTE ON TERMINOLOGY

Gender-based violence: For the purposes of this monitoring methodology, the term gender-based violence is used in line with the ERA Policy Agenda and the Zero-tolerance code of conduct as an umbrella term. It is intended to cover any and all terms that are used in national or regional policies with the intention to address any form of violence, including but not limited to sexual harassment, sexual violence, sexualised violence, gender harassment, , as well as physical violence, psychological violence, economic violence, online violence, or institutional violence and others. The monitoring methodology recognises that other terms may be used in national contexts such as social safety, with the intention to counteract gender-based violence. This methodology also recognises differences in the terms and approaches adopted by national or regional authorities. It aims to capture these differences, with a view to monitoring – over time – potential convergence in the terminology used and initiatives taken at the EU level and across Member States in response to policy coordination efforts in the European Research Area in the area of inclusive gender equality and gender mainstreaming.

4.2 DEFINITIONS

The below provided definitions of terms, formulations and indicators are intended to facilitate the understanding of the meaning of terms used in the proposed monitoring tool.

Some of the terms below are taken over from the section on Definitions in the Zero-tolerance code of conduct and the terminology used in the [UniSAFE Toolkit](#), in order to ensure consistency in the terms used in the EU.

All forms of gender-based violence taken seriously and investigated

This means that all incidents of gender-based violence—regardless of their perceived severity—are treated with attention and care, not minimised or ignored. This entails the commitment to enable safe reporting and ensure that every case is followed by a fair, timely, and impartial inquiry. Investigations must be grounded in victim/survivor-centred and trauma-informed principles, recognising the full continuum of violence, from subtle misconduct to severe abuse. The seriousness of each act is assessed not only by legal standards but also by its context and impact. This commitment reflects a zero-tolerance approach and institutional responsibility for addressing all forms of gender-based violence.

Bystanders

A bystander is an individual who witnesses or becomes aware of a potentially harmful or violent situation but is not directly involved as a victim or perpetrator. Sometimes, bystanders have the power to intervene, speak out, or take action to prevent or stop the harm from occurring (UniSAFE toolkit).

Capacity building

Capacity-building initiatives focus primarily on training, educating, supervising, mentoring, and facilitating mutual learning activities (along with other knowledge-sharing methods) aimed at addressing gender-based violence for various target groups. Ideally, capacity-building efforts should involve all students and staff, though it can be difficult to engage perpetrators, specific vulnerable groups, as well as leadership. While tailored, targeted training initiatives are essential for specific groups, mandatory introductory/induction and awareness-raising programmes may be necessary to establish a shared understanding of gender-based violence across the institution.

Embedded in the institutional change approach

Academia is marked by power imbalances, abusive cultures, and extreme competition, which constitute root causes of gender-based violence. Addressing gender-based violence therefore requires more than isolated measures; it necessitates embedding comprehensive policies within a broader strategy of institutional change.

Evaluation

Evaluation encompasses the systematic and objective assessment of a planned, ongoing or completed intervention, its design, implementation and results. Typical aims of evaluation are to determine relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact or sustainability. Evaluation also refers to the process of determining the worth or significance of an intervention (OECD 2023).

Gender-based violence acknowledged as a problem in the policy

In alignment with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, this policy item is intended to capture whether gender-based violence is clearly recognised as part of the policy document and the issue is named as a problem for the higher education and/or research sectors.

Gender-based violence as a systemic issue, not isolated incidents

In alignment with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, this item is intended to capture whether gender-based violence is understood as a systemic issue, rooted in power dynamics and structural inequalities. This perspective challenges the notion that gender-based violence consists of isolated, individual incidents or rare occurrences. Instead, it recognises that such violence is embedded within broader societal systems that perpetuate inequality. In these systems, marginalised groups and minorities are disproportionately affected by violence.

Initiative

An initiative refers to a specific activity, intervention, or step that is taken to address gender-based violence. Importantly, interventions can be undertaken by national/regional authorities with or without a formal policy as a framework. Initiatives are concrete measures put in place to address the issue of gender-based violence. They are more focused and short-term compared to policies. They can involve day-to-day activities, such as an awareness campaign, training, or providing support services for survivors.

Intersectional nature of violence

Gender-based violence is inherently intersectional, as it arises from and is perpetuated by overlapping systems of inequality and discrimination, such as those based on gender, race, ethnicity, (im)migration status, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, disability, and other forms of social marginalisation as well as functional differences (including contractual status). Intersectionality means that individuals experience gender-based violence differently depending on their unique combination of identity markers and positions, which shape their exposure to harm, the impact of violence, and their access to and experience of support systems. For example, women from marginalised racial or ethnic communities, LGBTQIA+ individuals, or people with disabilities face heightened risks of violence due to compounded stereotypes, structural inequalities, and barriers to justice. In addition, the research and higher education are marked by hierarchical structures that place people at distinctively different levels of power and authority, whereby some enjoy strong statutory protection while others work under precarious contracts and yet others are 'just' students. Recognising the intersectional nature of gender-based violence is essential to addressing its root causes, tailoring prevention and response measures.

Laws/Legislation

Law or legislation refers to laws and statutes that are enacted by national/regional governmental bodies. They are legally binding and establish the legal framework with which policies, interventions, and behaviours must align. Legislation mandates the rights and responsibilities of individuals and institutions regarding gender-based violence, setting legal standards and consequences for non-compliance. Legislation typically has broad application at the EU, national, or regional levels and can cover multiple sectors. It applies to all institutions and individuals within its jurisdiction, including HEIs, and ensures a consistent legal approach to gender-based violence.

- ***Dedicated law***

A legally binding document which formalises explicitly and specifically the commitment to addressing gender-based violence or any form thereof in higher education and/or research at the national or regional level. Importantly, a dedicated law may cover a wider range of institutions (e.g., all public employers which include higher education and/or research and innovation institutions).

- ***More general law***

A more general law means an overarching legally binding document that can be applied to addressing gender-based violence in research and innovation and/or higher education. For the purpose of this monitoring, 'more general' applies to the scope of gender equality issues addressed (e.g. not specific to gender-based violence but gender equality more broadly) and the scope of definitions (e.g., not only gender-based violence but also violence against women).

Monitoring

Monitoring encompasses a continuing process that involves the systematic collection or collation and analysis of data (on specified indicators or other types of information). It provides the management and other stakeholders of an intervention with indications of the extent of implementation progress, achievement of intended results, occurrence of

unintended results, use of allocated funds and other important intervention and context-related information (OECD 2023).

Objective

An objective is a specific, measurable goal that a policy/action aims to achieve in addressing gender-based violence. It defines the intended outcome or impact, providing a clear focus and direction for implementation. Objectives guide the development and evaluation of policies and initiatives by outlining what should change, improve, or be achieved—such as reducing incidents of gender-based violence, increasing reporting rates, enhancing support for survivors, and/or ensuring accountability.

Partnership

Partnerships—which can be internal or external to the institution—relate to the involvement of relevant actors at all levels, such as governmental agencies, civil society organisations, service providers, trade unions, and staff and student associations. External partners complement the available skills, competencies and expertise available within the institution. As well as cooperation and liaison with legal, police and criminal justice organisations and professionals, partnerships include close liaison with and learning from NGOs and other organisations with expertise in gender-based violence.

Policy

Policy is a document that encompasses a coherent set of measures with a clear vision and comprehensive strategy for action to address a public policy issue.

- ***Dedicated policy***
A document which formalises explicitly and specifically the commitment to addressing gender-based violence or any form thereof in research and innovation and/or higher education at the national or regional level adopted by a national or regional authority. A dedicated policy may cover a wider range of institutions (e.g., all public employers including higher education and/or research and innovation institutions).
- ***More general policy***
A more general policy means an overarching document that addresses gender-based violence in research and innovation and/or higher education as one area covered by the policy. For the purpose of this monitoring, ‘more general’ applies to the scope of gender equality issues addressed (e.g. not specific to gender-based violence but gender equality more broadly) and the scope of definitions (e.g., not only gender-based violence but also violence against women). More general policies can be a gender equality policy, a research and innovation policy, a higher education policy, a policy to counteract violence against women or other policy with a broader remit applicable to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.
- ***Policy embedded in or aligned with European Research Area policy***
This item intends to capture whether the national policy is aligned with or embedded in (e.g., through explicit reference) the European Research Area policy, such as the ERA Policy Agenda, the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, the EU Pact for R&I, the

Ljubljana Declaration or any other relevant Council conclusions and recommendations or Commission policies.

- ***Policy embedded in or aligned with other related policies at the national level (e.g. gender equality policy/strategy, Gender Equality Plan requirement etc.)***

This item intends to capture whether the national policy is aligned with any other national/regional policies. For example, once ratified, the Council of Europe's Convention on Preventing and Counteracting Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (known as the Istanbul Convention) provides a comprehensive legal framework for preventing and responding to gender-based violence. Another example may be the existence of a national or research-funder requirement for Gender Equality Plans to be in place aligned with the GEP eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe, which includes gender-based violence as one of the thematic recommended areas.

Precautionary measures

Precautionary or interim measures refer to actions that the respected institution reasonably takes to ensure the safety of a reporting party and possible other persons who may be at risk during a complaints or disciplinary process and to prevent their work or studies from being negatively impacted. To ensure the protection of individuals, whether they submit an informal or formal complaint, it is considered good practice to ask the person what they need and expect from the institution. Any protective actions taken should be tailored to their specific needs while observing the principle to keep the burden of the measures balanced between the parties so that the whole burden is not on the responding party. Examples of precautionary measures to safeguard students include offering options such as transferring to another class, attending online classes, or changing supervisors.

Priority groups

Research shows that specific groups are at great risk of being exposed to various forms of violence (such as women and LGBTQIA+ researchers facing intersectional inequalities based on ethnicity, nationality, economic background, disability and chronic illness, religion and other), or doctoral and postdoctoral fellows in precarious working conditions. The label 'priority groups' is therefore intended to capture whether the national/regional policy explicitly names any such groups as priority groups targeted by the policy.

Public consultation conducted in the policy drafting stage

Public consultation is a process where policy-makers seek input from the general public or specific groups on a proposed policy, plan, or decision. It is usually time-bound and formal, with a focus on gathering feedback. Public consultations are often open to anyone who wants to participate. They can take the form of public surveys, written consultations, public hearings, or online consultation platforms. Public consultation serves to engage diverse perspectives from affected groups to better define the issues under consideration and explore potential solutions. The level of consultation can vary, ranging from collecting views and needs to seeking feedback on policy proposals.

Stakeholder engagement conducted in the policy drafting stage

Stakeholder engagement is a structured process of identifying, consulting, involving, and collaborating with individuals, groups, and organisations that have a vested interest in or

are affected by a public policy. Stakeholder engagement is conducted to increase legitimacy and effectiveness, ensure inclusiveness, ownership and sustainability of policy solutions proposed. Stakeholder engagement during the drafting stage of public policy can take various forms. These include consultative methods like surveys, focus groups, public hearings, and stakeholder meetings; and collaborative approaches such as working groups and policy labs. Community-driven approaches, including listening sessions, local consultations, and storytelling, help capture grassroots perspectives, while partnerships with NGOs, unions, and cross-sector dialogues foster broader participation. Continuous feedback loops, monitoring committees, and targeted outreach for marginalised groups ensure diverse voices are heard and integrated into the policy-making process.

The stakeholder engagement formats in relation to gender-based violence in higher education/research and innovation may include dialogues with umbrella organisations, university associations, ombudsmen in higher education and research institutions, student and staff associations and unions, social workers, and NGOs working with victims, survivors, and bystanders.

Strategy

A strategy is a plan of action designed to achieve specific goals related to preventing and addressing gender-based violence. It outlines how an institution will implement its policy and address the specific challenges it faces in tackling gender-based violence. Strategies are typically more specific and actionable than policies. They break down goals into concrete steps, setting priorities, allocating resources, and defining timelines. Strategies focus on the "how", that is how the institution will carry out its efforts to counteract gender-based violence. This includes detailed actions, stakeholder involvement, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. A strategy might focus on specific initiatives such as increasing awareness among students, training staff on how to handle complaints, or creating support systems for survivors of gender-based violence.

Trauma-informed approach

A trauma-informed approach is closely related to a victim-centred approach and is based primarily on the 'do-no-harm' principle. It focuses on maximising the safety of the victim/survivor throughout the process, in physical, psychological, and emotional terms, in order to prevent re-traumatisation or secondary victimisation. Acknowledging that victims/survivors can manifest a diverse array of reactions and responses, it underscores the importance of rejecting any stereotypical notions about victims/survivors in order to ensure comprehensive support for all in need and to accurately gauge the level of trauma and distress experienced (National SART Guidelines Development Group 2023).

The goal of a trauma-informed approach is to care for the victim/survivor and assist in the initiation of the healing process. It emphasises understanding the prevalence and effects of trauma, promoting safety and trust, and empowering survivors to regain control over their lives. Much like a victim-centred approach, its key principles include safety, trustworthiness, choice, collaboration, and empowerment (National SART Guidelines Development Group 2023).

Victim/Survivor

Persons with experience of gender-based violence are referred to as ‘victims/survivors’ because these terms acknowledge that these individuals may identify differently in relation to their experience. Although the term ‘victim’ is a legal definition within the criminal justice system used for persons who have experienced a crime, ‘survivor’ is often used as an empowering term to convey that a person has started the healing process.

Victim/survivor-centred approach

Adopting a victim-centred approach means putting the needs and priorities of victims/survivors and bystanders of violence at the forefront of any response. Key elements of a victim-centred approach include listening to victims/survivors, avoiding re-traumatisation, and systematically focusing on their safety along with pro-active risk assessment and safety planning, rights, well-being, autonomy, expressed needs, and choices, thereby giving back as much control to the victim(s) as feasible and ensuring an empathetic, sensitive, and non-judgemental delivery of services and assistance (UN Women 2019; UNHCR 2024; European Institute for Gender Equality 2024). These principles are aligned with the Victims’ Rights Directive, especially in terms of the emphasis on enhancing the safety of victims and reducing risk (European Commission 2024).

It also entails providing comprehensive support services and centring victims’/survivors’ voices in decision-making throughout the process, including in disciplinary procedures. A victim-centred approach builds on the principles of empowerment, trust, safety, accountability, and justice. The shift towards a victim-centred approach reflects the growing recognition of victim/survivor needs and the failures of punitive, re-traumatising approaches, a better understanding of the impact of trauma, and an emphasis on long-term healing (UN Women 2019; UNHCR 2024; European Institute for Gender Equality 2024).

Whole-of-institution approach

A whole-of-institution approach to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research refers to a comprehensive, coordinated, and systemic strategy that engages all parts of an institution (leadership, academic units, administration, students, staff, and support services) in the prevention of and response to gender-based violence. It is grounded in leadership commitment, integrated and transparent policies and procedures, ongoing prevention and education efforts, accessible victim/survivor-centred support services, and inclusive, intersectional practices. This approach emphasises participation from all institutional actors, embeds gender-based violence prevention into core missions such as research and teaching, and relies on data collection, monitoring, and public accountability to ensure effectiveness and continuous improvement.

Zero-tolerance approach

A zero-tolerance approach means taking seriously any form of gender-based violence, including micro-aggressions, in higher education institutions and research institutions. Because gender-based violence is a continuum, a zero-tolerance approach focuses on capturing the entire spectrum of unacceptable behaviours, starting with and moving on from those instances that are less noticeable, to cultivate an institutional culture in which there is no form of gender discrimination. In this sense, a zero-tolerance approach considers any instance of gender-based violence as requiring to be addressed.

5 MONITORING TOOL FOR POLICIES TO COUNTERACT GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN THE ERA

5.1 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

The monitoring tool consists of a questionnaire that will be used for data collection from each national/regional system. The questionnaire will be administered through a professional online survey platform.

Respondents: Public authorities from the respective national systems.

Project team: The GenderSAFE Task 5.2 team will administer the monitoring and conduct the analysis.

Reflecting the contents and recommendations of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, below is a proposal for the data collection tool for national/regional authorities. The objective is to monitor policy adoption at Member State—and where relevant regional—level for EU level benchmarking.

The first section of the monitoring tool aims to collect data on the laws, policies and initiatives in place to address gender-based violence; the latter sections are structured along the three pillars of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

The framework developed for the purpose of monitoring national/regional policies to counteract gender-based violence in the ERA is presented below in full detail, including:

- the exact questions and the response sheets
- technical instructions for how to answer the questions

The questionnaire starts with an introductory text (Box 1, below).

Box 1. Introductory text

Dear survey participant,

We extend our warm thanks for your participation in this survey about national/regional policies to counteract gender-based violence in the European Research Area (ERA). Your contribution is important for monitoring the progress of these policies in line with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct adopted by the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality (European Commission 2024).

Context

This survey is part of a monitoring exercise conducted in the first instance within the framework of the EU-funded GenderSAFE project. The project has proposed to develop a monitoring methodology for counteracting gender-based violence in the ERA, which in turn will inform the exchange of information and mutual learning practices.

In the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, the ERA Forum Sub-group members have agreed to structure its recommendations under three pillars:

- Commitment
- Action
- Accountability

Each of these pillars contains a list of recommendations which are reflected in this monitoring tool.

Your input is essential for drawing an accurate picture regarding the advances in national/regional policies to counteract gender-based violence in your country as well as across the ERA.

Thank you for your time and input.

For any questions please contact [to be supplied].
 For data projection issues please see [to be supplied].

On behalf of the GenderSAFE team
 [name surname]
 [position in the project]
 [institution]

5.2 THE QUESTIONNAIRE

Section 1. Overview of national/regional laws, policies and initiatives

LAWS, POLICIES AND INITIATIVES IN PLACE: INTRODUCTORY TEXT

This section asks information about laws, policies and initiatives that address gender-based violence in relation to higher education and/or research and innovation. These can be dedicated laws, policies and initiatives addressing specifically gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation (for a definition see above). Importantly, these laws, policies and initiatives must address gender-based violence or its forms in relation to higher education and/or research and innovation even if these are one of other covered types of entities (e.g. documents covering all public employers).

Secondly, these can also be broader laws or policies on violence against women, research and innovation policies or gender equality policies.

Lastly, ad hoc initiatives may be in place such as information or awareness raising campaigns, requests for information including information requested for annual reports of higher education and/or research and innovation institutions.

For laws, only the title, year of adoption and year of an amendment if relevant, and link to the document are requested.

For policies and initiatives, four pieces of information are requested (title, policy/initiative owner; time frame; and whether it is publicly available, and if so a link to the policy/initiative).

Additional detailed information is requested for the main/most comprehensive law/policy/initiative in place. If a dedicated policy/initiative for HEIs and research organisations is adopted in line with the definitions above, respondents are asked to provide the detailed information about this policy/initiative. If a dedicated policy/initiative is not available in the national/regional context, national/regional authorities are requested to provide information about the most comprehensive policy/initiative at the national level.

Table 1. Indicative assessment of the existence of a law/policy/initiative to address gender-based violence in HE and/or R&I

Colour coding	Explanation
Comprehensive	A dedicated policy OR law OR both is in place
Developing	A more general policy OR law OR both, AND a dedicated initiative are in place
Intermediary	A more general policy OR law is in place OR dedicated initiatives are in place
Emerging	A National Action Plan or equivalent policy, to counteract all forms of gender-based violence and/or violence against women without a specific mention of higher education and/or research is in place
Absent	A general law to address gender equality and/or violence against women is in place

Questions	Instructions for completion
<p>Q1.1. Is a law/policy/initiative in place dedicated to gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation at the national/regional level?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially – Please specify [text box]</p> <p>If yes or partially to Q1.1, please provide further information.</p>	<p>For a definition of a dedicated policy and dedicated law, see →Dedicated policy in place and Dedicated law in place in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of an initiative, see →Initiative in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>Filter: If yes or partially, continue to Q1.1.1 to 1.1.4. if No to Q1.1, jump to Q1.2.</p>
<p>INFORMATION ON LAWS/POLICIES/INITIATIVES IN PLACE LISTED IN Q1.1 (DEDICATED POLICY IN PLACE)</p> <p>Please provide the following information ON THE DEDICATED LAWS/POLICIES/ INITIATIVES IN PLACE</p> <p>Q1.1.1 Please indicate the title of the law/policy/initiative in place: [text box]</p> <p>Q1.1.2 Which authority is the owner of the law/policy/initiative (the responsible national/regional authority)? [text box]</p> <p>Q1.1.3 Is the law/policy/ initiative publicly available? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes Link to law/policy/initiative (national language) Link to law/policy/initiative in English (if available) <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – Please specify [text box]</p> <p>Q1.1.4 What is the period covered by the law/policy/initiative? <input type="checkbox"/> Fixed period <input type="checkbox"/> Unspecified (no end date defined) <input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Information not available</p>	<p>The name of the law/policy/initiative must be provided. If no title is specified, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>The responsible national/regional authority must be identified in Q1.1.2. If this information is missing, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For Q1.1.2, if the law/policy/initiative is publicly available, a link must be provided. If 'Other' is selected, please provide a specific explanation; otherwise, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For Q1.1.3, the duration of the law/policy/initiative must be indicated. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.2. Is a more general law or policy in place at the national/regional level, which addresses gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation as part of a wider remit?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q1.2, please tick all that apply:</p>	<p>Q1.2 If the answer is 'Yes', at least one law/policy/initiative title must be provided. If no title is specified, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of a more general law and a more general policy, see →More general law and More general policy in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> General legislation to counteract gender-based violence and violence against women in all its forms (including the ratification of the Istanbul Convention) <input type="checkbox"/> A National Action Plan to counteract all forms of gender-based violence and violence against women <input type="checkbox"/> A national gender equality strategy addressing inter alia gender based violence <input type="checkbox"/> A national/ regional (ministerial) policy on higher education mentioning inter alia gender-based violence in any of its forms <input type="checkbox"/> A national/ regional (ministerial) policy on research and innovation mentioning inter alia gender-based violence in any of its forms <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]	<p>For a definition of an initiative, see →Initiative in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>Filter: If yes, continue to Q1.2.1 to 1.2.4. if No to Q1.2, jump to Q1.3.</p>
INFORMATION ON ALL LAWS/POLICIES IN PLACE LISTED IN Q1.2 (MORE GENERAL LAW / POLICY)	
<p>Please provide the following information ON ALL THE LAWS/POLICIES IN PLACE</p> <p>Q1.2.1 Please indicate the title of the law/policy/initiative in place: Title of the law/policy/ initiative [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.2 Which authority is the owner of the law/policy (the responsible national/regional authority)? [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.3 Is the law/policy publicly available? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes Link to policy (national language) Link to policy in English (if available) <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – Please specify [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.4 What is the period covered by the law/policy? <input type="checkbox"/> Fixed period <input type="checkbox"/> Unspecified (no end date defined) <input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Information not available</p>	<p>The title of the law/policy/initiative must be provided. If no title is specified, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>The responsible national/regional authority must be identified in Q1.2.1. If this information is missing, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For Q1.2.2, if the law/policy/ initiative is publicly available, a link must be provided. If 'Partially' is selected, a specific explanation is required; otherwise, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For Q1.2.3, the duration of the law/policy/ initiative must be indicated. If no timeframe is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.3. Are there any other initiatives to address gender-based violence in higher education and/or research at the national/regional level that could not be listed above? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q1.3, please provide further information:</p>	<p>Q1.3 If the answer is 'Yes', further information must be provided. If no further information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>If the answer is 'No', this indicates an absence of any initiative at the national or regional level to address gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.</p> <p>For a definition of an action, see →Initiative in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>Filter: If yes, continue to Q1.3.1 to 1.3.4. if No to Q1.2, jump to Q1.4.</p>
INFORMATION ON THE INITIATIVES IN PLACE LISTED IN Q1.3 (INITIATIVES)	
Please provide the following information ON ALL THE LAWS/POLICIES IN PLACE	

<p>Q1.3.1 Please indicate the title of the initiative in place: Title of the initiative [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.2 Which authority is the owner of the initiative (the responsible national/regional authority)? [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.3 Is the initiative publicly available? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes Link to policy (national language) Link to policy in English (if available) <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – Please specify [text box]</p> <p>Q1.2.4 What is the period covered by the initiative? <input type="checkbox"/> Fixed period <input type="checkbox"/> Unspecified (no end date defined) <input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Information not available</p>	
	<p>Filter: if No to Q1.1 AND Q1.2 AND Q1.3, jump to Q1.14.</p>
<p>Please select the MAIN LAW/POLICY/INITIATIVE IN PLACE and provide information only about this MAIN LAW/POLICY/INITIATIVE. If a dedicated law/policy/initiative has been adopted, information about this law/policy/initiative should be provided as a priority unless more comprehensive provisions are contained in another document.</p>	<p>Programming note: technical programming solution to selecting the main law/policy/initiative from the ones listed above</p>
<p>Q1.4. Has public consultation been conducted in the drafting stage? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know</p>	<p>Q1.4 If the answer is 'Yes,' it confirms that public consultation took place.</p> <p>If the answer is 'No' or 'I don't know,' no further action is required.</p> <p>If the answer 'Other' is selected, please provide further information.</p> <p>For a definition of public consultation, see →Public consultation conducted in the policy drafting stage in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q1.5. Has stakeholder engagement been conducted in the drafting stage? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know</p> <p>If yes to Q1.5, please specify the stakeholders involved in the process</p>	<p>Q1.5 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one stakeholder group must be selected.</p> <p>If no stakeholder is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>If the answer is 'No' or 'I don't know,' no further action is required.</p> <p>If the answer 'Other' is selected, please provide further information.</p> <p>For a definition of stakeholder engagement, see →Stakeholder engagement conducted in the policy drafting stage in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>Filter: If no to Q1.5 jump to Q1.6.</p>
<p>Q1.5.1 Please specify the stakeholders involved in the process: <input type="checkbox"/> Specialised NGOs</p>	

<input type="checkbox"/> Researchers/experts on gender-based violence <input type="checkbox"/> Student initiatives and associations <input type="checkbox"/> Staff organisations/trade unions <input type="checkbox"/> Survivor groups <input type="checkbox"/> Ministries and government departments <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]	
<p>Q1.6. What types of misconduct are covered in the policy? Please provide the terms used in the original language: [text box] Please provide the closest English translation of the terms (if an exact translation is unavailable, please describe the term's closest meaning): [text box]</p> <p>Please provide any other relevant information on the terminology used at the national/regional level, in particular if different terms are used in different laws/policies/initiatives. [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.6 The respondent is requested to provide both the terms in the original language and their closest English translation. If no terms are provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.7. What types of institutions are covered by the law/policy/initiative? Please select all that apply:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Public Higher Education Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Private/non-public Higher Education Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Public-Private Higher Education Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Public research institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Private research institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Public research funding organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Private research funding organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Public administration bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]	<p>Q1.7 At least one type of institution must be selected. If no institution is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.8. Is a budget allocated in the law/policy/initiative for its implementation?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know <p>If yes or other to Q1.8, please specify the amount of the budget (in national currency) allocated and for what period of time (e.g. annual budget available, a total budget for the policy duration) and the types of initiatives that the budget can be used for and provide any other relevant information: [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.8 If the answer is 'Yes,' please provide details on the budget amount, duration, and usage.</p> <p>If 'Other' is selected, please provide an explanation.</p> <p>As a priority, information should be provided on budgets to implement the law/policy/initiative in higher education/research and innovation.</p> <p>If a budget information is available but it cannot be determined which portion is allocated specifically for higher education/research and innovation, please include this information in the text box.</p> <p>If these details are missing, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.9. Does law/policy/initiative provide for making financial resources available to the institutions covered by the law/policy/ initiative?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <p>If yes to Q1.9, please specify the total amount of the financial resources for institutions to support work to counteract gender-based violence and for what period of time (e.g. annual budget available, a total budget for the policy duration) and the types of initiatives that the budget can be used for: [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.9 If the answer is 'Partially,' please provide an explanation.</p> <p>If no explanation is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q1.10. Does the law/policy/initiative explicitly endorse the Zero-tolerance code of conduct?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<p>Q1.10 If the answer is 'Partially,' please provide an explanation.</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially – [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable (e.g., if adopted prior to 2024 when the Zero-tolerance code of conduct was published)	If no explanation is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.
<p>Q1.11. Is the law/policy/initiative embedded in or aligned with other national/regional policies (e.g. gender equality policy/strategy, Gender Equality Plan requirement, the Istanbul Convention if ratified etc.)</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially - please explain: [text box] <p>If yes to Q1.11, please indicate which policy specifically: [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.11 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one policy must be specified.</p> <p>If 'Partially' is selected, please provide an explanation.</p> <p>If no policy or explanation is given, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For an explanation of policy embedded in/aligned with other related national/regional policies, see →Policy embedded in / aligned with other related policies at the national level (e.g. gender equality policy/strategy, Gender Equality Plan requirement etc.) in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q1.12. Does the law/policy/initiative explicitly define any concrete objectives related to counteracting gender-based violence?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Partially - please explain [text box] <p>If yes to Q1.12, please specify the objectives: [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.12 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one objective must be specified.</p> <p>If 'Partially' is selected, please provide an explanation.</p> <p>If no objective or explanation is given, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of an objective, see →Objective in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q1.13. Has the law/policy/initiative specified above been launched to coordinate national/regional policy with the recent EU developments (the Ljubljana Declaration, GEP eligibility criterion, ERA Policy Agenda 2022 - 2024)? (Please select all that apply)</p> <input type="checkbox"/> No, laws/policies/initiatives to address gender-based violence in higher education and research were in place prior to the recent EU developments. <input type="checkbox"/> No, laws/policies/initiatives to address gender-based violence emerged around the same time but this did not stem from EU policy coordination. Please specify the impetus for the national developments: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, laws/policies/initiatives have been launched in relation to the adoption of the GEP eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, laws/policies/initiatives have been launched in relation to the work on and adoption of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, laws/policies/initiatives have been launched in relation to the 2024 Directive on counteracting violence against women and domestic violence. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, laws/policies/initiatives have been launched in relation to other developments at the EU level. Please specify which were the developments at the EU level specifically: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, laws/policies/initiatives were in place at the national level prior to the developments at the EU level and the national policy has been revised to reflect the EU developments (e.g., the Ljubljana Declaration, the Zero-tolerance code of conduct, the Council Recommendation on Attracting, Retaining...).	<p>Q1.13 If 'Yes' is selected, at least one EU development must be specified.</p> <p>If 'Other' is selected, please provide an explanation.</p> <p>If no EU development or explanation is given, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For an explanation of policy embedded in ERA policy, see →Policy embedded in / aligned with European Research Area policy in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]	
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To assess the policy outlook, the following questions intend to capture current plans in relation to the adoption of laws/policies/initiatives. Based on the responses obtained, a policy outlook will be included in the report using the “traffic light” as specified below.

Questions	Instructions for completion
<p>Q1.14. Are there plans to strengthen the existing national/regional law/policy/initiative to address gender-based violence? Please select all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to adopt a new dedicated law with provisions addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to amend a dedicated law with provisions addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to adopt a new general law with provisions addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to amend a general law with provisions addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to adopt a new general policy with provisions addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to adopt a new dedicated policy on gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to advance policy provisions in the dedicated policy that is in place (including updating policy in response to policy review and consultation)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to advance policy provisions in the general policy that is in place (including updating policy in response to policy review and consultation)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to introduce a new initiative by the national/regional authority</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to renew an initiative by the national/regional authority</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p>Please provide detailed comment on the planned changes including new developments in alignment with the Zero-tolerance code of conduct and its recommendations in terms of Commitment, Action and Accountability: [text box]</p>	<p>Q1.14 Please provide a comment on any and all changes indicated.</p> <p>For a definition of a dedicated law in place, see →Dedicated policy in place in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a more general law, see →More general policy in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a dedicated policy in place, see →Dedicated policy in place in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a more general policy, see →More general policy in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of an initiative, see →Initiative in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q1.15. Are there plans to weaken the existing national/regional law/policy/initiative to address gender-based violence?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen commitments in the general law in place</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen commitments in the dedicated law in place</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen policy commitments in the general policy in place</p>	<p>Q1.15 Please provide a comment on any and all changes indicated.</p> <p>For a definition of a dedicated law in place, see →Dedicated policy in place in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a more general law, see →More general policy in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen policy commitments in the dedicated policy in place <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen policy commitments in the general initiative in place <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, there are plans to loosen policy commitments in the dedicated initiative in place <input type="checkbox"/> Other Please provide detailed comment on the planned changes: [text box]	For a definition of a dedicated policy in place, see → Dedicated policy in place in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS . For a definition of a more general policy, see → More general policy in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS . For a definition of an initiative, see → Initiative in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS .
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For the purposes of assessing the policy outlook, the examples of possible developments can take the following form:

- **Strengthened policy:** planned adoption of new dedicated or general laws, policies or initiatives and the amendment of existing dedicated laws, policies and initiatives introducing new policy items. These can be related to:
 - **Commitment elements** of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct (e.g., recognising the systemic nature of gender-based violence, defining priority groups, defining the cross-cutting zero-tolerance principles including victim-centred and trauma-informed approaches or an intersectional perspective),
 - **Action elements** (e.g., introduction or reinforcement of preventative and protective measures, new measures on prevalence/incidence and data collection, partnerships, provision of services, investigation procedures and sanctioning), and
 - **Accountability elements** (e.g., introduction or reinforcement of reporting to the national/regional authority on actions and measures taken by the institutions; introduction or reinforcement of reporting to the national/regional authority on the budgets allocated for policy implementation; holding senior management accountable for policy implementation; introduction or reinforcement of policy monitoring by the national authority including indicators; introduction or reinforcement of policy evaluation by the national authority; introduction or reinforcement of sanctions for non-compliance).
- **Loosened policy:** change in the scope from gender-based violence to misconduct or harassment or any removal of references to gender; failure to renew gender equality policy including sections addressing gender-based violence; elimination of a GEP eligibility criterion at the national level including counteracting gender-based violence.

Policy outlook	Explanation
Strengthened policy	There are documented plans by the national/regional authority to strengthen the policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation in EITHER: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - upcoming national/regional laws dedicated to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation OR - upcoming national/regional generic laws OR - upcoming national/regional policies dedicated to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation - upcoming national/regional generic policies OR - upcoming national/regional initiatives.

Unchanged policy	There are no documented plans to either strengthen or loosen policies addressing gender-based violence in higher education or research and innovation by the national/regional authority.
Loosened policy	There are documented plans by the national/regional authority to loosen policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education/research and innovation in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - upcoming national/regional laws OR - upcoming national/regional policies OR - upcoming national/regional initiatives

Section 2. Commitment

This section focuses on the content of the main policy selected in the previous section. It focuses on cross-cutting elements specified in the 'Commitment' section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct. These include the recognition of the systemic nature of gender-based violence, definition of priority groups, and the inclusion of the defined zero-tolerance principles.

The following Table 2 provides an indicative assessment of how the national/regional laws/policies/initiatives will be assessed against the elements contained in the Commitment section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

Table 2. Indicative assessment of national/regional laws/policies/initiatives in terms of the Commitment elements

Colour coding	Explanation
Comprehensive	4 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND at least 7 priority groups and protected characteristics are defined AND at least 4 of the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above
Developing	3 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND at least 5 priority groups are defined AND at least 3 the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above
Intermediary	2 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised AND/OR at least 3 priority groups are defined AND/OR at least 2 the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above
Emerging	1 or 2 elements of the systemic nature of gender-based violence are recognised OR at least 3 priority groups are defined OR at least 1 of the zero-tolerance principles are addressed in the main policy/action selected above
Absent	The main policy/action selected above does not recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence, does not define priority groups and does not define any of the zero-tolerance principles

Filter from previous section: Information is requested only on the main law/policy/initiative selected for closer examination (starting with Q1.4)

Questions	Instructions for completion
<p>Q2.1 Does the main law/policy/initiative recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence (i.e. instances not being regarded as a series of isolated incidents but instead as systematic manifestations of structural inequalities)?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q2.1, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of unequal power relations in higher education and/or research and innovation</p>	<p>Q2.1 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one of the listed elements must be selected. If no element is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For an explanation of the systemic nature of gender-based violence, see → gender-based violence as a systemic issue, not isolated incidents in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of the meaning of embedded in the institutional change approach, see → Embedded in</p>

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of the existence of violence along a continuum of violence and abuse (from microaggressions to severe acts of violence)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recognition that efforts to address gender-based violence should be embedded in an institutional change approach (such as through Gender Equality Plans)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Recognition of the intersectional nature of gender-based violence</p> <p>Please provide further information related to the recognition of the systemic nature of gender-based violence (optional): [text box]</p>	<p>the institutional change approach in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of the intersectional nature of gender-based violence, see → Intersectional nature of gender-based violence in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q2.2 Does the main law/policy/initiative define priority groups to be considered?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q2.2, please indicate all the priority groups and protected characteristics defined in the policy:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Chronic illness</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Disability</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Neurodiversity</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ethnic and racial minority groups</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Gender identity</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Migration status</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Religion</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Sexual orientation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Socioeconomic status</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mobile staff</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Mobile students</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Precarious employment (e.g., temporary/short-term contacts)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Certain age groups (e.g., early-career researchers)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify which groups: [text box]</p>	<p>Q2.2. If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one of the listed groups must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of specific priority groups, see → Specific priority groups in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q2.3 Does the main law/policy/initiative define zero-tolerance principles in the law/policy/initiative?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q2.3, please select all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Victim-centred or victim/survivor-centred approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Trauma-informed approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Whole-of-institution approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Adoption of a zero-tolerance approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commitment to taking all forms of gender-based violence seriously</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Commitment to investigating all reports of incidents of gender-based violence</p>	<p>Q2.3 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one zero-tolerance principle must be selected. If no principle is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of a victim/survivor-centred approach, see → Victim/survivor-centred approach in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS</p> <p>For a definition of a victim/survivor, see → Victim/Survivor in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a trauma-informed approach, see → Trauma-informed approach in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of a whole-of-institution approach, see → Whole-of-institution approach in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For a definition of the zero-tolerance approach, see → Zero-tolerance approach in → 4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p> <p>For an explanation of all forms of gender-based violence, see → All forms of gender-based</p>

	violence taken seriously and investigated in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.
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Section 3. Action

This section focuses on the content of the main policy selected in the first section. It focuses on the content of the law/policy/initiative specified in the 'Action' section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

The section is organised into two parts, with the aim of capturing both items that are **mandatory/required by the law/policy/initiative** and those that are **recommended by the national/regional authorities**. Hence, the first section addresses items that the national/regional law/policy/initiative requires (Q3.1 and its sub-questions) and the second which addresses items that the national/regional law/policy/initiative recommends (Q3.2 and its sub-questions). These items reflect the UniSAFE 7P framework which underpins the recommended areas of action in the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

The following Table 3 provides an indicative assessment of how the national/regional laws/policies/initiatives will be assessed against the elements contained in the Action section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

Table 3. Indicative assessment of national/regional laws/policies/initiatives in terms of the Action elements

Colour coding	Explanation
Comprehensive	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 9 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - institutional policy in place - institutional monitoring and evaluation - prevalence/incidence and data collection measures - preventative measures - capacity building for senior leadership - capacity building for middle management - protective measures - investigative procedures - disciplinary measures and sanctions - provision of services - partnerships
Developing	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 7 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - institutional policy in place - institutional monitoring and evaluation - prevalence/incidence and data collection measures - preventative measures - capacity building for senior leadership - capacity building for middle management - protective measures - investigative procedures - disciplinary measures and sanctions - provision of services - partnerships
Intermediary	The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 5 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - institutional policy in place - institutional monitoring and evaluation - prevalence/incidence and data collection measures - preventative measures - capacity building for senior leadership - capacity building for middle management - protective measures - investigative procedures

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - disciplinary measures and sanctions - provision of services - partnerships
Emerging	<p>The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends that at least 2 of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - institutional policy in place - institutional monitoring and evaluation - prevalence/incidence and data collection measures - preventative measures - capacity building for senior leadership - capacity building for middle management - protective measures - investigative procedures - disciplinary measures and sanctions - provision of services - partnerships
Absent	<p>The national/regional authority requires and/or recommends none of the actions below be put in place by the institutions covered by the policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - institutional policy in place - institutional monitoring and evaluation - prevalence/incidence and data collection measures - preventative measures - capacity building for senior leadership - capacity building for middle management - protective measures - investigative procedures - disciplinary measures and sanctions - provision of services - partnerships

Filter from previous section: Information is requested only on the main law/policy/initiative selected for closer examination (starting with Q1.4)

Questions	Instructions for completion
REQUIRED ACTIONS	
<p>Q3.1 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require actions to address gender-based violence to be taken by the covered institution?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p>Q3.1 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one specific action must be listed in Q3.1.1 to Q3.1.9. If no action is indicated, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>If the answer is 'No' to Q3.1, this means that national/regional authorities do not require any action to be taken by the covered institutions.</p> <p style="color: purple;">Filter: If the answer is "No" in Q3.1, Q3.1.1 to Q3.1.9 are filtered out. Jump to Q3.2.</p>
<p>Q3.1.1 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require any action to be taken by the covered institutions in relation to their own institutional policy?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.1, please select all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Requirement to adopt an institutional policy</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Requirement to monitor the implementation of an institutional policy</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Requirement to define monitoring indicators on an implementation of an institutional policy</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Requirement to evaluate the effectiveness of an institutional policy</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.1 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one listed action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p>Q3.1.2 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require establishing prevalence or incidence at the institutional level?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.2, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institution-wide prevalence studies or surveys <input type="checkbox"/> Other types of surveys which contain questions about gender-based violence (e.g. student wellbeing surveys, staff satisfactions surveys, climate assessments or cultural audits to evaluate norms, attitudes, and safety perceptions within the institution or its organisational units etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Administrative data collection, centralisation and analysis (such as number of formal complaints lodged, informal disclosures, or the use of support services) <input type="checkbox"/> Online reporting data analysis, including anonymous disclosures and usage trends <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring of disciplinary and grievance procedures, including outcomes <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-disaggregated collection <input type="checkbox"/> All gender identity groups considered in the data collection <input type="checkbox"/> Intersectional analysis possible <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.2 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one element must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>By prevalence, a total number of cases in a population at a given time is meant.</p> <p>By incidence, a number of new cases in a given period is meant.</p>
<p>Q3.1.3 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require any preventative actions to be taken by the covered institutions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.3, please select all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Communication campaigns <input type="checkbox"/> Awareness raising (e.g. about unacceptable behaviours and reporting mechanisms such as posters, events, digital communications) <input type="checkbox"/> Mandatory induction training/workshops for students (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Mandatory induction training/workshops for staff <input type="checkbox"/> Voluntary induction training/workshops for students (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Voluntary induction training/workshops for staff <input type="checkbox"/> Continuous staff training (excluding ad hoc, one-off training) <input type="checkbox"/> Continuous student training (excluding ad hoc, one-off training) <input type="checkbox"/> Active bystander training <input type="checkbox"/> Proactive risk assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Safe and inclusive campus design, including adequate lighting, signage, and accessible spaces (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Integration of the issue of gender-based violence into curricula, research ethics, and training programmes <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.3 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one preventative action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p>Q3.1.4 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require capacity building for those in senior and middle leadership roles?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.4, please tick all groups that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Senior management at university or faculty levels (Presidents, Provosts, Rectors, Deans) in HEIs or Directors or equivalent at research organisations</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Middle management (such as group leaders, Heads of Departments etc.)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Staff in supervisory roles</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.4 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one group must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q3.1.5 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require any protective actions to be taken by the covered institutions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.5, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Contact place/staff member to receive reports</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Anonymous reporting channels available</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Non-anonymous informal complaint channels available</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Non-anonymous formal complaint channels available</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Training for staff responsible for case management</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Risk assessments and safety planning tailored to individual cases (e.g., no contact orders or separation measures)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Confidentiality safeguards to protect personal information during and after reporting</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Protection against retaliation</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Precautionary measures</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Access to safe spaces or temporary housing on or near campus</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Follow-up and case monitoring to ensure measures remain appropriate and effective</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.5 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one protective action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of precautionary measures, see →Precautionary measures in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q3.1.6 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require the introduction of investigative and/or disciplinary actions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.6, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Define an investigative procedure including principles and investigation committee set-up</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Define disciplinary measures and sanctions</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Open communication on investigation outcomes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Open communication on disciplinary actions and sanctions given</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.6 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one element must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p>Q3.1.7 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require any action to be taken by the covered institutions in relation to the provision of services?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.7, please select all types of services that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Crisis intervention services <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological/therapeutic <input type="checkbox"/> Medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual and reproductive health services <input type="checkbox"/> Medical referrals <input type="checkbox"/> Legal advice and support <input type="checkbox"/> Academic or workplace accommodations (e.g. extensions, changes in supervision, relocation) <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.7 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one service type must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q3.1.8 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly require partnerships between the obligated organisations and other institutions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.1.8, with which type of partners? Please tick all elements that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other higher education and/or research organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Health services <input type="checkbox"/> Community organisations (e.g., community work, community projects, community development, community empowerment, community building, and community mobilization) <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Student organisations and initiatives <input type="checkbox"/> Staff organisations and/or trade unions <input type="checkbox"/> Legal bodies <input type="checkbox"/> International partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified</p>	<p>Q3.1.8 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one type of partnership must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of partnerships, see →Partnerships in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
RECOMMENDED ACTIONS	
<p>Q3.2 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend (but not require) actions to address gender-based violence to be taken by the covered institution?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p>Q3.2 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one specific action must be listed in Q3.2.1 to Q3.2.9. If no action is indicated, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>If the answer is ‘No’ to Q3.2, this means that national/regional authorities do not recommend that any action be taken by the covered institutions.</p> <p>If the answer is ‘No’ to Q3.2.1, Q3.2.2, Q3.2.3, Q3.2.4, Q3.2.5, Q3.2.6, Q3.2.7, Q3.2.8, or Q3.2.9, this means that the national/regional authority does not recommend any action to be taken by the institutions listed below in Q3.1.1 to Q3.1.9.</p> <p>Filter: If the answer is “No” in Q3.2, Q3.2.1 to Q3.2.9 are filtered out. Jump to Q3.3.</p>
<p>Q3.2.1 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend actions to be taken by the covered institutions in relation to their own institutional policy?</p>	<p>Q3.2.1 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one listed action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.2.1, please tick all that apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendation to adopt an institutional policy <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendation to monitor the implementation of an institutional policy <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendation to define monitoring indicators on an implementation of an institutional policy <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendation to evaluate the effectiveness of an institutional policy <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified 	
<p>Q3.2.2 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend establishing prevalence or incidence at the institutional level?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.2.2, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Institution-wide prevalence studies or surveys <input type="checkbox"/> Other types of surveys which contain questions about gender-based violence (e.g. student wellbeing surveys, staff satisfactions surveys, climate assessments or cultural audits to evaluate norms, attitudes, and safety perceptions within the institution or its organisational units etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Administrative data collection, centralisation and analysis (such as number of formal complaints lodged, informal disclosures, or the use of support services) <input type="checkbox"/> Online reporting data analysis, including anonymous disclosures and usage trends <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring of disciplinary and grievance procedures, including outcomes <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-disaggregated collection <input type="checkbox"/> All gender identity groups considered in the data collection <input type="checkbox"/> Intersectional analysis possible <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified 	<p>Q3.2.2 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one element must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q3.2.3 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend any preventative actions to be taken by the covered institutions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q3.2.3, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Communication campaigns <input type="checkbox"/> Awareness raising (e.g. about unacceptable behaviours and reporting mechanisms such as posters, events, digital communications) <input type="checkbox"/> Mandatory induction training/workshops for students (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Mandatory induction training/workshops for staff <input type="checkbox"/> Voluntary induction training/workshops for students (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Voluntary induction training/workshops for staff <input type="checkbox"/> Continuous staff training (excluding ad hoc, one-off training) <input type="checkbox"/> Continuous student training (excluding ad hoc, one-off training) 	<p>Q3.2.3 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ at least one preventative action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Active bystander training <input type="checkbox"/> Proactive risk assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Safe and inclusive campus design, including adequate lighting, signage, and accessible spaces (where relevant) <input type="checkbox"/> Integration of the issue of gender-based violence into curricula, research ethics, and training programmes <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified 	
<p>Q3.2.4 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend capacity building for those in senior and middle leadership roles?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <p>If yes to Q3.2.4, please tick all groups that apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Senior management at university or faculty levels (Presidents, Provosts, Rectors, Deans) in HEIs or Directors or equivalent at research organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Middle management (such as group leaders, Heads of Departments etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Staff in supervisory roles <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified 	<p>Q3.2.4 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one group must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q3.2.5 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend any protective actions to be taken by the covered institutions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <p>If yes to Q3.2.5, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Contact place or staff member that receives reports <input type="checkbox"/> Anonymous reporting channels available <input type="checkbox"/> Non-anonymous informal complaint channels available <input type="checkbox"/> Non-anonymous formal complaint channels available <input type="checkbox"/> Training for staff responsible for case management <input type="checkbox"/> Risk assessments and safety planning tailored to individual cases (e.g., no contact orders or separation measures) <input type="checkbox"/> Confidentiality safeguards to protect personal information during and after reporting <input type="checkbox"/> Protection against retaliation <input type="checkbox"/> Precautionary measures <input type="checkbox"/> Access to safe spaces or temporary housing on or near campus <input type="checkbox"/> Follow-up and case monitoring to ensure measures remain appropriate and effective <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified 	<p>Q3.2.5 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one protective action must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of precautionary measures, see →Precautionary measures in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>Q3.2.6 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend introducing investigative or disciplinary actions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <p>If yes to Q3.2.6, please tick all elements that apply:</p>	<p>Q3.2.6 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one element must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> Define an investigative procedure including principles and investigation committee setup <input type="checkbox"/> Define disciplinary measures and sanctions <input type="checkbox"/> Open communication on investigation outcomes <input type="checkbox"/> Open communication on disciplinary actions and sanctions given <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified	
<p>Q3.2.7 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend any actions to be taken by the covered institutions in relation to provision of services?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<p>Q3.2.7 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one service type must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>If yes to Q3.2.7, please select all types of services that apply:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Crisis intervention services <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological/therapeutic <input type="checkbox"/> Medical care <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual and reproductive health services <input type="checkbox"/> Medical referrals <input type="checkbox"/> Legal advice and support <input type="checkbox"/> Academic or workplace accommodations (e.g. extensions, changes in supervision, relocation) <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified	<p>Q3.2.8 Does the main law/policy/initiative explicitly recommend partnerships between the obligated organisations and other institutions?</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	<p>Q3.2.8 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one type of partnership must be selected. If no option is selected, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>For a definition of partnerships, see →Partnerships in →4.2 DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND INDICATORS.</p>
<p>If yes to Q3.2.8, please tick all elements that apply:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> Other higher education and research organisations <input type="checkbox"/> Health services <input type="checkbox"/> Community organisations <input type="checkbox"/> NGOs <input type="checkbox"/> Student organisations and initiatives <input type="checkbox"/> Staff organisations and/or trade unions <input type="checkbox"/> Legal bodies <input type="checkbox"/> International partnerships <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not specified	

Section 4. Accountability

This section focuses on the content of the main policy selected for closer examination in the previous section. It focuses on the content of the law/policy/initiative specified in the 'Accountability section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct and refers to oversight mechanisms, reporting obligations, independent evaluation, and enforcement or sanctioning related to gender-based violence policies.

The following Table 4 provides an indicative assessment of how the national/regional laws/policies/initiatives will be assessed against the elements contained in the Accountability section of the Zero-tolerance code of conduct.

Table 4. Indicative assessment of national/regional laws/policies/initiatives in terms of the Accountability elements

Colour coding	Explanation
Comprehensive	At least five of the following accountability elements are in place: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators - The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level - The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken - The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation - The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation - The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.
Developing	At least four of the following accountability elements are in place: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators - The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level - The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken - The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation - The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation - The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.
Intermediary	At least three of the following accountability elements are in place: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators - The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level - The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken - The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation - The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation - The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.
Emerging	At least one of the following accountability elements are in place: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The national/regional authority conducts policy monitoring at the national/regional level, including through indicators - The national/regional authority conducts policy evaluation at the national/regional level - The national/regional authority requires reports from the institutions on institutional policies, actions and measures taken - The national/regional authority requires reports on the institutional budgets allocated for policy/action implementation - The national/regional authority holds senior management of the institutions accountable for institutional policy implementation - The national/regional authority has sanctions in place for non-compliance by the institutions covered by the policy.
Absent	None of the above

Questions	Instructions for completion
Q4.1. Does the main national/regional law/policy/initiative require the institution covered by the policy to report regularly to the national/regional authority on actions taken?	Q4.1 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one form of reporting requirement must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete .

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If yes to Q4.1, please tick all elements that apply: <input type="checkbox"/> formal reporting <input type="checkbox"/> informal reporting e.g., through participation in mutual exchanges <input type="checkbox"/> on a regular basis <input type="checkbox"/> on an ad-hoc basis</p> <p>Please comment on the reporting requirement: [text box]</p>	
<p>Q4.2. Does the main national/regional law/policy/initiative require the institutions covered by the policy to report on the budgets allocated for addressing gender-based violence?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If yes to Q4.2, please tick all elements that apply: <input type="checkbox"/> This is part of reporting on the policy implementation (as in Q4.1). <input type="checkbox"/> This is part of other reports required from the covered institutions.</p>	<p>Q4.2 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one form of reporting requirement must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q4.3. Does the national/regional policy hold the senior management (rectors, provosts) at the institutional level responsible for policy implementation?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If yes to Q4.3, please specify: [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.3 If the answer is 'Yes,' at least one form of the formalised responsibility of senior management must be selected. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q4.4. Does the national/regional authority monitor the implementation of the law/policy/initiative in place?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box] <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable</p> <p>If yes to Q4.4:</p> <p>Q4.4.1. What is the monitoring frequency? <input type="checkbox"/> Annual <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>Q4.4.2. Who conducts the monitoring? <input type="checkbox"/> The policy owner <input type="checkbox"/> An external contractor <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify [text box]</p> <p>Q4.4.3. Is a budget available for the monitoring? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.4 If the answer is 'Yes,' please provide additional information on the national/regional policy monitoring. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p>Q4.4.4. What form does the monitoring take? Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify: [text box]</p> <p>Q4.4.5. Is it foreseen for the monitoring to be used for further policy development?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q4.4.5., please specify: [text box]</p>	
<p>Q4.5. Does the main national/regional law/policy/initiative contain any monitoring indicators?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If yes or other to Q4.5, please specify: [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.5 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ please provide additional information on the national/regional policy monitoring indicators. If no information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q4.6. Are any sanctions or consequences foreseen in the event the covered institutions do not comply with the national/regional law/policy?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable</p> <p>If yes or other to Q4.6, please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If no to Q4.6.1 Is there any follow-up with the non-compliant institutions? Please specify: [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.6 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ please provide additional information on the sanctions or consequences. If no information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>Q4.6 If the answer is ‘No,’ please provide additional information on any potential follow-up with the non-compliant institutions. If no information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q4.7. Does the national/regional authority evaluate the effectiveness of the national/regional policy?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>If yes to Q4.7:</p> <p>Q4.7.1. What is the evaluation frequency?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Annual</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Periodic - please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Ad-hoc – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>Q4.7.2. Who conducts the evaluation?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> The policy owner</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> An external contractor</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify [text box]</p> <p>Q4.7.3. Is a budget foreseen for the evaluation?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p>Q4.7.4. What form does the evaluation take?</p>	<p>Q4.7 If the answer is ‘Yes,’ please provide additional information on the national/regional policy evaluation. If no selection is made, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>

<p>Please tick all that apply.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p> <p>Q4.7.5. Is it foreseen for the evaluation to be used for further policy development?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes to Q4.7.5, please specify: [text box]</p>	
<p>Q4.8. Has there been specific public messaging around the policy adoption and launch?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other</p> <p>If yes to Q4.8:</p> <p>Q4.8.1. What form did the public messaging take? Please tick all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Public launch event</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Press conference</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Press release</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Social media campaign</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other - please specify: [text box]</p> <p>Q4.8.2. If relevant, who was the highest-ranking figure in this public messaging (e.g., minister, deputy minister etc.)? Please specify: [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.8.1 If the answer is 'Yes,' please provide additional information on the form of public messaging. If no information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>Q4.8.2 If the answer is 'Yes,' please provide additional information on the highest-ranking figure involved in the public messaging as relevant. If no information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p>
<p>Q4.9. Does the national/regional law/policy/initiative include provisions to counteract multi-site serial misconduct by same perpetrators at different institutions?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes – please specify: [text box]</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other – please specify: [text box]</p>	<p>Q4.10 If the answer is 'Yes,' please provide additional information on the contents of the p provisions to address multi-site serial misconduct (such as prevention, obligation to inform, precautionary measures etc.). If no additional information is provided, the answer is considered incomplete.</p> <p>Please select other in the event any discussions have occurred on the topic in the national context.</p>

Thank you for completing this questionnaire.

6 EU-LEVEL INDICATORS

This section defines proposed high-level indicators for EU-level monitoring.

6.1 ADOPTION INDICATORS

- The number of European countries that have adopted a dedicated law and/or policy to address gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.
- The number of European countries that have adopted a more general law and/or policy that encompass addressing gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.
- The number of European countries that have explicitly endorsed the Zero-tolerance code of conduct or some of its principles in their laws/policies/initiatives on gender-based violence in higher education and research.
- The number of European countries that allocate a budget to implement laws/policies/initiatives against gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.

6.2 COMMITMENT INDICATORS

- The number of European countries that recognise the systemic nature of gender-based violence in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.
- The number of European countries that promote trauma-informed approaches in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.
- The number of European countries that promote victim/survivor-centred approaches in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.
- The number of European countries that recognise the intersectional nature of gender-based violence in their laws/policies to address gender-based violence.
- The number of European countries whose laws/policies contain provisions targeting specific priority groups (e.g., LGBTQIA+, ethnic minorities, individuals with disabilities, early-career researchers etc.).

6.3 ACTION INDICATORS

Comprehensive policies

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies adopt comprehensive policies to address gender-based violence.

Institutional change

- The number of European countries whose laws/policies embed the issue of gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation within institutional change (such as through Gender Equality Plans).

Monitoring and evaluation requirement for the covered institutions

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies monitor their policies to address gender-based violence.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies evaluate the effectiveness of their policies to address gender-based violence.

Prevalence and/or incidence data collection

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies collect gender-disaggregated prevalence and/or incidence data at the institutional level.

Awareness raising campaigns

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct awareness-raising campaigns (e.g. about unacceptable behaviours and reporting mechanisms).

Training and capacity building

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct preventive training sessions for staff.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct preventive training sessions for students if relevant.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for senior management of higher education and/or research institutions.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for staff members in managerial and supervisory positions in higher education and/or research institutions.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct capacity building sessions for staff responsible for case handling.
- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies conduct active bystander intervention training.

Reporting mechanisms

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies to have reporting mechanisms in place.

Partnerships

- The number of European countries that require or recommend that the institutions covered by the laws/policies engage in partnerships with internal and/or external stakeholders.

6.4 ACCOUNTABILITY INDICATORS

Leadership accountability

- The number of European countries whose national/regional laws/policies ascribe responsibility to institutional senior management (such as presidents, rectors and, at the lower level, deans) for the implementation of institutional policies.

Disciplinary actions and sanctions

- The number of European countries with sanctions in place for the institutions covered by the national/regional laws/policies that are in breach of the law/policy.

Prevention of multi-site serial misconduct at different institutions

- The number of European countries that have put in place concrete measures to prevent multi-site serial misconduct by perpetrators at different institutions.

Policy monitoring by the national authority

- The number of European countries that monitor the implementation of their national/regional laws/policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.

Policy evaluation by the national authority

- The number of European countries that evaluate the effectiveness of their national/regional laws/policies to counteract gender-based violence in higher education and/or research and innovation.

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